

NPOWER
BALANCING N & P FLOWS

D.8.2 Ethics Principles

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The NPower Project

NPower aims to reduce nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) emissions and rebalance nutrient flows across key sectors in Europe. By advancing nutrient recovery technologies, best management practices (BMPs), and governance measures, the project will contribute to more efficient and circular nutrient use, minimising environmental impact while supporting agricultural and industrial sustainability.

Running for four years from January 2025, NPower will:

- Develop an innovative N/P budgeting software model to analyse and optimise nutrient flows across five key emitting sectors.
- Demonstrate six nutrient recovery technologies to produce sustainable fertilisers.
- Promote 20 best management practices to improve nutrient efficiency and reduce emissions.
- Design and implement governance measures to support effective nutrient management policies at local, regional, and EU levels.
- Facilitate knowledge transfer across four Regional Clusters (RCs) in Spain, Belgium, Finland, and Ireland to ensure EU-wide applicability.

Spain will serve as the main demonstration site, implementing recovery technologies, while the other RCs will assess their applicability and potential replication in their respective contexts.

Led by a consortium of 25 partners from across Europe, NPower integrates expertise from research, industry, and policy, covering the entire N/P value chain. This collaboration will provide practical, scalable solutions to optimise nutrient cycles and support the EU's sustainability goals.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
BMP	Best Management Practice
CAP	Common Agriculture Policy
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
Dnn	Deliverable Number
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IGM	Innovative Governance Measures
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MAT	Multiactor Transition group
Mnn	Month (of project)
N/P	Nitrogen and Phosphorus
OS	Open Science
PA	Practical Abstract
RC	Regional Cluster
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
soLCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UWWTD	Urban WasteWater Treatment Directive
WP	Work Package

1. Executive summary

This document constitutes the deliverable D8.2 Ethics Principles which aims at ensuring a rigorous, sound and comprehensive Ethical Framework, thus responding to the necessities that social research and environmental issues arise, particularly regarding the requirements and methodologies to ensure citizens' rights, security and welfare. The document also provides the procedures for informed consent.

N/P emissions from human activities have environmental and health impacts, that imply a matter of social good and ethical, normative and legal frameworks. Considering the complex interrelationships between biogeochemical transformations caused by anthropogenic activities, NPower commits to 3 ethical principles: environmental integrity, social and environmental justice, and sustainability and stewardship.

NPOWER Consortium will ensure that project procedures align with Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), including the consideration of gender and diversity issues, the ethical implications of risk management, and the responsiveness towards social values.

Special attention will be given to public participation, that represents a core pillar along the project: NPower ethics principles will ensure data protection procedures are set and respected along the lifetime of the project aligning with the Data Management Plan, guaranteeing that participation of stakeholders in project activities is supported by Informed Consent Forms, such as the provided in the Annex.

The Ethics Principles is a living document that will be launched on M6 (June 2025) and revised and updated along the project lifecycle.

2. Introduction

Excessive nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) emissions from human activities result in severe environmental consequences: 75% of global agricultural soils are polluted by N and P, with these nutrients being the most prevalent pollutants in aquatic ecosystems, leading to eutrophication¹. They are also significant air pollutants, with vast consequences at human health and environmental levels: e.g., nitrogen oxides (NOx) contributing to over 49,000 premature deaths in the EU in 2021². Moreover, N/P losses represent a waste of valuable resources; e.g., impacting on rising fertiliser prices, tripled between 2020 and 2022. All these figures are also a matter of social good and ethical, normative and legal framework behind the societal and environmental progress.

2.1 Ethics principles applied to environmental issues

The ethical framework underpinning nutrient pollution management navigates the complex interrelationship between anthropogenic biogeochemical alterations and their multidimensional impacts across socio-ecological systems.

While N and P fertilizers help increase crop yields and support food security, their overuse leads to long-term environmental harms, such as loss of ecosystem services, degraded water quality, health issues from contaminated drinking water. Moreover, the excess N/P persists in soils and waterways for decades, creating “dead zones” that may take centuries to recover; nitrous oxide (N₂O) is 300× more potent than CO₂, accelerating global warming and ocean acidification³.

The impacts mentioned above may manifest with disproportionate severity in socioeconomically vulnerable communities with inadequate infrastructure, raising questions of environmental justice⁴ and distributional equity⁵.

Therefore, the following 3 principles are proposed as key strands for NPower: environmental integrity, social and environmental justice, and sustainability and stewardship.

¹<https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/zero-pollution/cross-cutting-stories/nutrients#:~:text=Reducing%20nutrient%20pollution%20is%20a,the%20EU%20nature%20restoration%20plan>

²<https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/air-quality-in-europe-2022/health-impacts-of-air-pollution>

³<https://phys.org/news/2021-07-nitrous-oxide-powerful-greenhouse-gas.pdf>

⁴ Environmental Justice refers to the equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, ensuring that all communities, particularly those historically marginalised, have the right to a healthy environment. Source: <https://oxford-review.com/the-oxford-review-dei-diversity-equity-and-inclusion-dictionary/environmental-justice-definition-and-explanation/>

⁵ Distributional equity refers to how costs and benefits are distributed between different actors. <https://economicstermslexicon.com/definitions/d/distributional-equity/>

2.1.1 Environmental integrity

The NPower project places environmental integrity as its foundational ethical imperative, establishing a comprehensive framework wherein all interventions must demonstrably contribute to ecosystem preservation and biogeochemical equilibrium restoration. It can be summarized in the following dimensions or aspects:

- Commitment to preventing further nutrient pollution and remediating existing contamination
- Recognition of ecosystem complexity and the interconnectedness of biogeochemical cycles
- Duty to protect biodiversity and ecological functions threatened by eutrophication.

This principle implies systematic emissions reduction protocols, biodiversity conservation mechanisms, and ecological balance maintenance within an integrated sustainability paradigm that prioritises long-term environmental resilience over short-term technological usefulness.

In sum, environmental integrity as an ethical pillar that demands the constriction of human nutrient outputs to what ecosystems can absorb, devoting to a moral commitment to the resilience and longevity of natural systems.

NPower is committed to environmental integrity through the N/P budgeting of key N/P emitting sectors in the region of Murcia (WP2) aimed at preventing nutrient pollution through a deeper knowledge on the interconnectedness of biogeochemical cycles in the Region of Murcia. Moreover, the demonstration of technologies for circularising N/P emissions (WP3) reflects the commitment to preventing further nutrient pollution.

2.1.2 Social and Environmental Justice

The second ethical pillar of NPower is Social and Environmental justice, which encompasses the following aspects:

- Equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens
- Prioritization of interventions in communities disproportionately affected by nutrient pollution
- Recognition of structural inequalities in access to clean water and environmental decision-making.

The first aspect is related to *distributive justice*, as a rigorous commitment to equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens related to nutrient flows and mitigation measures, while the second aspect refers to *recognitional justice*, reflecting on the disproportionate effects of nutrient pollution on vulnerable or marginalized groups (for instance, rural communities reliant on well water that becomes nitrate-contaminated, fishermen and tourism workers facing economic losses from algal blooms, or neighbours of large livestock farms enduring foul air and health risks) (Resnik et al., 2018). This pillar also encompasses

intergenerational justice, as excess nutrient runoff and accumulation due to mismanagement today leads to long-term ecosystem degradation, and global justice, as Europe's demand for feed and fertilizer can drive nutrient mining and pollution abroad (phosphate rock) raising questions of Europe's ethical responsibility beyond its borders.

This pillar is reflected in EU policies through regulations like the Nitrates Directive⁶, which requires the member states to identify Nitrate Vulnerable Zones, ensuring that regulations like fertilizer limits are enforced and prioritising remediation efforts in communities already hit by pollution; the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)⁷, subsidizing farmers to adopt practices that reduce off-site impacts. Moreover, the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) establishes stricter water treatments and duties and responsibilities for towns and cities, while strengthening the polluter-pays principle by ensuring that those responsible for pollution bear the costs of remediating it and recognises the lack of access to clean water and sanitation of certain groups.

NPower addresses the social and environmental justice pillar demands through a strongly participative methodology, setting up Multiactor Transition Groups (MATs), representing different sectors (agriculture and animal husbandry, other primary sectors, water and waste management, energy and transport and other industrial sectors) that will be grouped in Regional Clusters (RCs) gathering representatives of the Quadruple Helix of innovation (WP1). The MATs will play a key role analysing regional features and context characteristics and promoting horizontal governance (WP4). Moreover, in WP6, the social LCA (SoLCA) will evaluate the impact of NPower solutions in society using SSH methodologies and evaluate the readiness to change for the adoption of new technologies or processes, aiming not only to reduce pollution overall but also do so in a way that does not unfairly disadvantage certain groups.

2.1.3 Sustainability and stewardship

The principle of sustainability in nutrient management emphasizes meeting current needs (food production, soil fertility) without compromising the ability of future generations and ecosystems to meet their own needs. It is closely linked to the idea of stewardship – the ethical duty to manage natural resources wisely and respectfully as trustees for those who come after us. Stewardship also contributes to maintain the feelings of fairness and legitimacy, that are important to effectiveness, especially in cases where success requires active participation on the part of the members of the group over time (Biermann and Kim, 2020).

In the context of N/P flows, this implies:

- moving from a linear “take-make-dispose” model of nutrient use to a circular economy model where nutrients are recycled and reused.

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1991/676/oj/eng>

⁷ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-2023-27_en

- Promoting resource efficiency optimisation protocols, avoiding waste is a moral good when resources like phosphate rock are finite.
- Preventing harm to future life, as unsustainable use today produces pollution but also threatens food security tomorrow.

NPower adopts a systems-based approach to resource governance based on circular economy principles. This methodological orientation facilitates the development of closed-loop nutrient management systems, and waste stream valorisation mechanisms that collectively minimise environmental footprints while maximising resource utilisation longevity across multiple temporal and spatial scales.

This principle is manifested in the EU's Circular Economy Action Plan and the revised Fertilising Products Regulation (2019/1009) by creating a single market for recycled fertilizers and setting contaminant limits, the EU is promoting ethical resource management while protecting health⁸. Policy implications of this pillar include investing in R&D for nutrient recovery technologies, incentivizing farmers to use recycled fertilizers (via subsidies or eco-schemes), and developing indicators to monitor nutrient circularity as part of sustainability metrics. The EU CAP 2023–27 moves in this direction by supporting eco-schemes for nutrient management and linking farm payments to sustainable practices.

In NPower, sustainability is reflected in the demonstration of N/P recovery technologies and recovered fertilizers (WP3), fostering circular economy. In addition, stewardship invoking the image of farmers and industries as “custodians” of soil, air and water, will be exemplified in the Best Management Practices (BMPs) identified and demonstrated with the feedback of relevant stakeholders in the Multiactor Transition Groups (WP4)

3. Ethics in the context of R & D

3.1 Open science

Open Science (OS) is, more than a requirement, an Ethical obligation to respond to complex and interconnected environmental, social, and economic challenges by providing solutions to advance environmental sustainability and respect for the planet's biological and cultural diversity, foster sustainable social and economic development and promote democracy and peace (UNESCO, 2021).

In addition, “Open science principles require that such communication with various societal stakeholders should not only be a one-way communication (academics inform the public about their research results) but instead should be a two-way communication, in which relevant stakeholders should have a significant impact on the formulation of research questions”(Düwell, 2019).

⁸https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/chemicals/fertilising-products_en#:~:text=,are%20imposed%20at%20EU%20level

The NPower Open Science Plan will be further developed in D8.1 Data Management Plan by CETENMA, aiming at “Transparency, accessibility, and solving societal challenges”.

3.2 Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is critical within the Ethical dimension of the project⁹. Specifically, in regards to: (a) Ethical research, including its lawful appropriateness and the issues concerning data privacy, as well as the considerations specifically concerning the involvement of deprived, marginalised or vulnerable collectives; (b) Research integrity, respecting academic freedom and human rights and supporting high-quality and transparent research; and (c) Social acceptability and alignment (see the sections on [Open Science](#) and [Ethics principles](#)).

In sum, RRI should consider, as stated verbatim by RRI Tools¹⁰ (Figure 1):

1. Diversity and inclusion: Be sensitive to research biases, include diverse voices and make results beneficial to a wider community.
2. Anticipation and Reflection: Think about the purposes and possible implications of your research and its outcomes and envisage all possible strategies and methods.
3. Openness and Transparency: Share objectives, methods and, whenever possible and appropriate, results, and inform about potential conflicts of interest.
4. Responsiveness and Adaptive Change: Be responsive to changes and external inputs, adapting research plans to changing social values and expectations.

Figure 1 Principles of RRI (source: RRI tools)

RRI should consider during the whole lifecycle and evaluate the following dimensions (Figure 2):

⁹ RRI tools relating to ethics <https://www.scishops.eu/rri-tools-relating-to-ethics/>

¹⁰ <https://rri-tools.eu/>

Figure 2 RRI dimensions (source: RRI tools)

Key specific RRI issues and process dimensions considered in NPower are reflected in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Key specific issues and process dimensions to consider in RRI (source: RRI tools)

3.3 Gender and diversity

Gender and diversity are relevant for ethics promoting gender equality by addressing the representation (or lack thereof) of women in research with the objective to reduce gender segregation.

The Gender Equality Strategy of the EU (European Commission, Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, 2020) aims to develop targeted measures to achieve gender equality, combined with strengthened gender mainstreaming. The Strategy is to be implemented with an intersectional approach to understand and respond to the ways in which sex and gender intersect with other personal characteristics/identities (i.e. socioeconomic class, racial or ethnic origin, religion

or belief, disability, age) and how these intersections contribute to unique experiences of discrimination¹¹, as a cross-cutting principle.

Gender issues primarily address:

- The horizontal and vertical participation of women in research to promote women in all fields where they are under-represented, as well as to increase female participation in management and decision-making positions.
- Structural change in research institutions aimed at eliminating structural barriers for women to increase their participation in scientific careers.
- Integration of gender in the content of research and innovation to ensure that women's needs and interests are adequately addressed. Explicit gender issues are rarely included in the content, and it is argued that research results are not valid or reliable if they only consider male research subjects.

The Gender Equality Strategy and the Framework for the integration and evaluation of inclusive gender analysis in research and innovation (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2025) recognise the role of a sex, gender and intersectional perspective in environmental issues such as the climate crisis and the need of an inclusive analysis to be integrated into R&I content, as environmental impacts involve several research fields. For instance, environment is a health determinant and women's bodies have been shown to be more vulnerable to pollutants such as nitrites than men's and likely to transfer the pollutants to their children (Farnworth et al., 2017; UNEP/SETAC, 2015); furthermore, it is important to analyse women's participation as farmers and landowners; in addition, women quite often bear the heaviest care burden needs in socioenvironmental disasters, partly related to the uneven distribution of unpaid household and care work. Gender differences may also be reflected in different perceptions of landscapes and pollution (Häfner et al., 2018), the adoption of conservation measures and acceptance of policies (Guo et al., 2019) and it should be considered in the design of innovative governance models and best practices.

Thus, NPower will integrate gender policy of the EU (including the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025) and Public Engagement and Responsible Research and Innovation inclusive approach, taking all measures to promote equal opportunities between all population groups, throughout all the project implementation, including:

- i. Workshops: The co-creation processes will be evaluated considering quantitative factors such as gender balance, and the MATs set up in WP1 will consider gender and diversity aspects in and stakeholder selection. KVC (as responsible for the methodology of the workshops) will also examine the results of workshops in WP1-WP5 with a gender perspective through balanced gender representation.
- ii. Online questionnaires: for instance those used in WP6 for social impact assessment, will contain a demographic section on gender following the

¹¹ <https://eige.europa.eu/thesaurus/terms/1263>

- two-step method (i.e., differentiating birth sex and gender identity) (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2020) to capture the nuances of each group and allow data disaggregation.
- iii. Practices and technologies: NPower will evaluate the adequacy of the demonstrated set of practices and technologies demonstrated in WP3 to the needs of different genders (such as different tendencies in fertilizing methods).
 - iv. Governance measures: the innovative governance measures analysed in WP5 will account for gender differences specific clusters and economic sectors and promote the inclusion of all genders in the adoption of N/P-limiting actions.
 - v. Recommendations: the developed recommendations for policy makers and local and regional administrations in WP6 will define a set of actions to be taken as to promote and ensure equal representation of all genders in the different stakeholder groups.
 - vi. D&C activities: The D&C strategy will take into account the complexity of target audiences, considering an intersectional approach, and messages and channels chosen in WP7 will be aimed at gender neutrality.
 - vii. Management and coordination: NPower coordinator, CETENMA, has a Gender Equality Plan in place. Partners will also follow the principles in their Gender Equality Plans and the principles and measures included in the present deliverable.

4. Ethics and public participation

4.1 Regulations:

All the activities developed along the project will comply with ethical principles and relevant national, EU and international legislation, for example, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (European Commission, 2012) and the European Convention on Human Rights (European Court of Human Rights, 1950). Provisions of Regulation (EU) 2016/679¹² (General Data Protection Regulation) principles of rights and consent and data processing as stipulated in Articles 6, 7, 10, 12, 25 and 35 (GDPR, 2018g) are shown to be highly relevant to the protection of research participants and service users.

Moreover, Regulatory compliance is within the scope of Task 1.1 Consolidation of actors from the 5 key N/P emitting sectors assessment, led by CETENMA and participating KVC. This project aligns with:

- The Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (known as General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR), repealing Directive 95/46/EC.

¹² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>

- Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector - the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (2000/c 364/01).
- Gender policy of the EU (European Commission, Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, 2020) and
- Public Engagement and Responsible Research and Innovation inclusive approach.

4.2 Stakeholder engagement: the Multi Actor Transition groups (MATs) and Regional Clusters (RCs)

In NPower five thematic MATs will be created and they will play a pivotal role in the project. The MATs cover the following themes: Agriculture, Other primary sectors, Waste/water management, Energy and Transport and Industry. In that sense, ethics matters are of especial relevance in WP1 (Establishment of multi-actor transition groups within EU Regional Clusters) as it is the WP coordinating the MATs (Figure 4). These groups will be involved in a series of activities in the different WPs led by the four Regional Clusters (RCs): RC1 Spain, RC2 Belgium, RC3 Finland and RC4 Ireland.

Stakeholder engagement will consider 3 levels of participation, further described in MATs methodology. These 3 levels will be adjusted according to the objectives of the project and the specific actions:

- Information level represents the provision of information from the project to the public, mainly carried out through the Communication and Dissemination activities in WP7 led by LOOP, such as attendance to events, or capacity building actions.
- Consultation level aims at obtaining feedback from stakeholders, but with little interaction, for instance through surveys or questionnaires collecting feedback for impact assessment in WP6 led by KVC.
- Collaborate level include the activities in which the stakeholders are directly engaged in decision-making or co-creation processes, such as the MATs workshops performed in WP1 led by MTU.

Figure 4 Distribution of MATs in the Regional Clusters and Regional Clusters leaders

4.3 Principles or values for involvement of participants

NPower participants' involvement follows a series of principles concerning community readiness and engagement and the evaluation of the engagement itself:

- *Community* readiness analyses the degree to which a community is ready to take action on an issue, in a specific, dimensional, and stratified way. Community efforts, knowledge of the efforts, leadership, willingness or awareness, knowledge and resources should be analysed prior to implementing public engagement methods.
- *Community engagement* and *Community participation* in workshops (i.e. to define Multiactor Transition Pathways) will promote the ownership of the project results.
- *Evaluation* of engagement and participatory processes will consider both quantitative factors (e.g. the number of stakeholders; gender balance; equitable representation of age groups and the diversity of social groups) and qualitative factors (e.g. the direct and indirect impact the stakeholders had on the processes, activities and decisions taken). Engagement will be evaluated in WP6 of the project and will follow the evaluation table presented in Figure 5.

Empowerment	<input type="checkbox"/> To plan for fostering or facilitating the policy making and long-term changes at social level		
	<input type="checkbox"/> To plan to minimise power imbalance and tokenism	<input type="checkbox"/> To enhance environmental education resources in and for the community	<input type="checkbox"/> To foster community bonds <input type="checkbox"/> To balance power as much as possible <input type="checkbox"/> Jointly defined agenda
Community engagement Based on co-creation, participation and involvement	To plan the IPR and co-ownership strategy addressing: <input type="checkbox"/> How to share results <input type="checkbox"/> How to provide ownership and co-authorship of the community <input type="checkbox"/> How funds and results could be shared <input type="checkbox"/> To research into methods for reaching an active involvement, participation of key persons: who? How?	<input type="checkbox"/> To address collective/communitarian expectations	<input type="checkbox"/> To ensure financial transparency <input type="checkbox"/> To plan for long-term financial and organisational support
		<input type="checkbox"/> To involve key stakeholders : environmentalists, civil society organisations, opinion leaders, consumers associations	<input type="checkbox"/> To continue with the strategic multistakeholder approach <input type="checkbox"/> Team Working
Community participation	<input type="checkbox"/> To participate in researchers' training on community participation , dissemination and implementation science		To enhance researchers' competences <input type="checkbox"/> Social skills <input type="checkbox"/> Linguistic skills <input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge of the community
Individual engagement	<input type="checkbox"/> To involve the community's stakeholders from the design phase	<input type="checkbox"/> To examine previous success cases	<input type="checkbox"/> To take into account how the individuals' self-efficacy in circular economy , climate change adaptation and other environmental issues can be enhanced
	<input type="checkbox"/> To provide well-tailored and enough information <input type="checkbox"/> To prevent false expectations <input type="checkbox"/> To ensure that the community is really willing to participate <input type="checkbox"/> To design culturally tailored material	<input type="checkbox"/> To assess the viability of snowfall recruitment through relatives, friends and immediate social networks. <input type="checkbox"/> To assess the convenience of social media , internet, online newspapers or similar media (newspapers, flyers)	<input type="checkbox"/> To consider individuals' altruistic motivations : engage and socialise, benefit others <input type="checkbox"/> To deliver enough resources including budget <input type="checkbox"/> To have appropriate administrative support
Individual involvement, compliance	<input type="checkbox"/> To ensure enough flexibility for participating	<input type="checkbox"/> To address individualistic expectations in potential participants	<input type="checkbox"/> To consider individuals' motivations <input type="checkbox"/> To think about potential secondary gains for enhancing the retainment
	Design	Recruitment	Engagement

Figure 5 Levels of involvement and involvement aim (adapted from Acha et al., 2021)

4.4 Data protection

As a first step, RC leaders have set up a stakeholder database hosted in NPower internal repository that will be available for all partners that will be able to consult the registered stakeholders and populate it as the project evolves.

As it will be stated in MATs Methodology (D1.2), in the KOM of the RCs a responsible for stakeholders' data will be appointed for each RC to ensure that NPower Data protection procedures are set and respected along the lifetime of the project.

Furthermore, in T8.3 (Data Management and Ethics), a Data Management Plan (D8.1) will include the procedures needed to ensure safe data collection, handling, and storage. The Data Management Plan will be updated in M23 (D8.3) and M47 (D8.4). However, some insights are given here, and alignment with the Data Management Plan will be ensured along the project implementation. Participation in project activities shall in any case be voluntary and informed. NPower activities will only involve adult participants, that will be fully able to provide explicit, written, free, specific, and informed consent to participate in any event and to sign the informed consent before it takes place. If vulnerable groups were involved, the informed consent provided by their legal guardians is required (who, in any case, must be adults who meet the conditions described above). Prior to taking part in the activities, participants will be informed about the NPower project, as well as about the scope and objectives of the specific activity (i.e. focus groups and/or workshop involving the MATs, etc.).

It is the duty of the beneficiary to ensure that invitations to participate in the activities it leads or implements contain transparent and easily understandable

information on the purpose of the project, the objective of the research, an informed consent procedure and a participation protocol. Reports and documentation shall be available in a language and terminology that can be fully understood by each participant. Participants who cannot be guaranteed this will not take part in NPower activities.

As recognized in Article 7.c. of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation: GDPR), participants “shall have the right to withdraw his or her consent at any time”. However, the withdrawal of consent “shall not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal”. In order to be able to exercise this right, and prior to the provision of informed consent, beneficiaries should make participants aware of the possibility of withdrawing at any time they wish without providing justification and, when the time comes, facilitate the effective exercise of this right.

Table 1 summarises the activities potentially involving data on the identification and recruitment of participants.

Table 1 NPower tasks and participants' involvement which could raise ethical requirements

Tasks	Description	Specification	Ethical issues potentially involved
T1.1	Consolidation of actors from the 5 key N/P emitting sectors	User data required for the stakeholder engagement	Data protection and Informed consent
T1.2	Launch of 5 multi-actor transition groups per RC.	User data required for the stakeholder engagement	
T2.1	Gathering data for N/P budgeting in the region of Murcia	Data will be collected through direct interaction with stakeholders (input from MATs in RC1 -with special support of practitioner representatives-, workshops, interviews and online surveys). D1.2 (MATs methodology) will define qualitative and quantitative methods to	Data protection and Informed consent RRI

Tasks	Description	Specification	Ethical issues potentially involved
		collect the information from the activities	
T4.1	Identification and selection of relevant BMPs at regional and EU level	This identification will be done with the help of the stakeholders involved in the MATs through the Regional Clusters (RCs). D1.2 (MATs methodology) will define qualitative and quantitative methods to collect the information from the activities	
T4.2	Demonstration of N/P balancing BMPs	The demonstration might be done by the stakeholders (specifically practitioners) involved in the RCs	
T5.1	Development of innovative governance measures.	RC leaders will organize meetings to discuss all governance measures with industry and research representatives and MATs in the 4 RCs will be gathered to analyze the project results. Multiactor transition pathways will be co-created. D1.2 (MATs methodology) will define qualitative and quantitative methods to collect the information from the activities	Data protection and Informed consent RRI
T5.2	Showcasing innovative governance measures.	Capacity building workshops organized by each RC targeting policy makers at local, regional, national and EU levels will be organised.	

Tasks	Description	Specification	Ethical issues potentially involved
T6.2	Social impact of NPower solutions.	Contact of participants to assess the social impact of NPower solutions through interviews, questionnaires and surveys. Methods will be defined in D1.2	
T6.3	Policy recommendations for regional and European regulatory instruments disseminated through targeted workshops	Contact workshop participants from European institutions, covenant of mayors, and network of local entities for the Agenda 2030.	
T7.1	Communication activities: PAs sent to stakeholders	Send PAs to concerned stakeholders.	
T7.2	Dissemination activities	Dissemination activities contacts.	Data protection and informed consent
T7.3	EU potential for replicating circularity	Potential contact for business opportunities consultations and mapping of key N/P sectors.	
T7.4	Exploitation strategy	Potential contact for the development of circular business models.	Data protection and Informed consent
T7.5	Synergies with relevant initiatives and platforms	Screening for relevant Regional Clusters, initiatives, projects, and platforms	

4.5 Informed consent procedures

Explicit informed consent by data subjects is a vital part of any process involving human subjects, to respect their rights of free choice and data privacy. The whole consortium will ensure that the potential subjects can reach a truly informed decision about whether or not to participate in the project. Their explicit informed consent must be given freely, without coercion, and must be based on a clear understanding of what participation involves, including any personal data to be processed and the purposes of the same. Each partner responsible for involving end-users will guarantee the collection of explicit consents, signed by representatives as stated above before any empirical activity affecting them, including but not limited to the collecting of personal data.

As in the case of data protection, consolidated hands-on guidance in this respect will be collected from relevant sources at an early stage of the project. A preliminary investigation has revealed some principles that should be considered for achieving informed consent from users participating in the project:

- Each potential subject must be adequately informed of the aims, methods, anticipated benefits and potential hazards of the research and any discomfort it may entail;
- The expected participation of individuals and the approximate duration of each activity must be informed in advance;
- Any documentation given to potential participants should be comprehensible, and there should be an opportunity for them to raise any issues of concern;
- Consent should be given in writing and records of consent should be maintained; considering the particularities in the workplace and the risks that it may entail; the following measures may be also considered;
- Workers representatives' consent: If workers are involved during their regular schedule, and if obtaining individual consent from each worker is not feasible, labour unions representatives will discuss and agree on the participation with the staff and then, sign the consent;
- Consent Form: The information in the consent form should be individualized and communicated in a way that is more sensitive to the needs of participants. The number of questions in the "Consent Form" has to be appropriate to participants' profile (high-skilled workers and managers, chiefs and directors, low-skilled workers, labour union officers, etc.), An example of template of NPower consent form is presented in Annex (further details in Data Management Plan), all partners should adapt it to their needs;
- Potential participants must be informed that they are free to withdraw consent to participation at any time;
- There should be a procedure for making complaints and participants should be made aware of this;

- All participants must be volunteers. Considerable care should be taken where consent is sought from those in a dependent position;
- Any inducement offered to participants should be declared and should be by appropriate guidelines.

4.5.1 Informed consent implementation during the NPower project

As previously introduced, NPower will collect and process various personal data, both online and offline. Additionally, the project may potentially process sensitive personal data (e.g., ideology, values/ beliefs, and even health conditions), that may be collected accidentally, even though avoiding these data will be actively sought. Therefore, some of the NPower activities that envisage involving human participants will require their informed consent to be carried out. The informed consent of participants will allow beneficiaries to: 1) process personal data; 2) obtain and use images and/or recordings of participants for project purposes only; and/or 3) observe workers in their workplace. Informed consent to the processing of personal data will be required for any activity involving some of the forms of processing of personal data identified in Article 4 (2) GDPR: collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction. In addition, informed consent will be required for video/audio recording or image taking for those activities for whose primary purpose it is essential, as well as for the dissemination tasks of the project.

The tasks presented in Table 2 may potentially require the collection of informed consent forms from the participants for their incorporation in the development of some of the activities foreseen in the framework of these tasks.

Table 2 NPower tasks that may require data privacy measures and informed consent

Tasks	Description	Justification
T1.1	Consolidation of actors from the 5 key N/P emitting sectors	Data consent for activities' participants
T1.2	Launch of 5 multi-actor transition groups per Regional Cluster.	Data protection of stakeholders (including incidental findings)

Tasks	Description	Justification
T2.1	Gathering data for N/P budgeting in the region of Murcia	Data protection of stakeholders (including incidental findings)
T4.1	Identification and selection of relevant BMPs at regional and EU level	Data protection of stakeholders (including incidental findings)
T4.2	Demonstration of N/P balancing BMPs	Data protection of stakeholders (including incidental findings)
T5.1	Development of innovative governance measures.	Data protection for meetings participants
T5.2	Showcasing innovative governance measures.	Data protection for workshop participants
T6.2	Social impact of NPower solutions.	Data protection for contacted participants to assess social impact.
T6.3	Policy recommendations for regional and European regulatory instruments disseminated through targeted workshops	Data protection for workshop participants
T7.1	Communication activities: PAs sent to stakeholders	Data protection for contacted stakeholders
T7.2	Dissemination activities	
T7.3	EU potential for replicating circularity	Data protection for contacted persons.
T7.4	Exploitation strategy	
T7.5	Synergies with relevant initiatives and platforms	

All volunteer research participants (e.g. stakeholders in MATs) will receive an informed consent form prior to the start of the research which they will be asked to sign and return signed. The informed consent form shall contain basic information on the project and the specific activity, written in an accessible language and translated into relevant languages where necessary. In addition, before the start of the activity, researchers will review the informed consent form. Participants may request access to the sheet both electronically and in hard copy. If the nature of the circumstances requires that the informed consent form be read and summarised verbally, the investigator will do so.

Following the confirmation that all participants have understood the basic information about the project and the specific activity, they will be asked to provide voluntary informed consent. All obtained consent will be freely given; no pressure will be put on participants to participate in the project. All participants will be allowed to ask questions and receive clear answers before making decisions about their participation.

Within the consent form, there will be reiterated the rights of the individual participants for them to consent to/opt to. The receipt of the signed informed consent form will ensure that all voluntary participants are aware of the data collection and processing that will occur within the scope of NPower.

The research participant will be asked to sign, date, and return the informed consent form. The participant and researcher will each retain one copy of the consent and information sheet. The completed consent sheet will be stored by the Data Controller that has collected it.

4.5.2 Incidental findings

Beyond the issues of data privacy, a broader range of ethics issues potentially arise when designing and implementing policy recommendations, simulations, protocols, and guidelines, or, in general, new products or services for stakeholders. One aspect is the input collected from persons' data; the situation is more sensitive if those data are sensitive personal data (e.g., incidentally discovered information about participants' ideology, values or health issues during a workshop). Also, information will be obtained from companies and industries, public administration officers and a vast range of civil society organisations, experts and researchers in workshops/conferences. Another way to obtain the information will be the interaction with public administrations, services and civil society organisations in everyday life. With regards to data collection, and beyond the issues of data privacy, incidental findings about private issues (e.g. religion, origins, political affiliations) may occur: these will be kept under the highest conditions of confidentiality and should not be collected or reported in any form by the researchers involved (more information in the section on Data Privacy).

5. Conclusion

According to the needs of environmental and social research that will take place in NPower, the following key aspects need to be overseen during the project execution:

- Accomplishment of RRI principles, research integrity and Open Access to Research, including the design of research protocols that ensure a high level of ethical commitment
- The design and implementation of adequately defined informed consent procedures, where required
Consideration of Public Participation guidelines, that will be further described in D1.2 MATs Methodology.

The Ethics Principles will be revised and updated along the project lifecycle.

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7. Annex. Informed consent template.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Project acronym	NPower
Project full name	Balancing Nitrogen and Phosphorus fLOWs by budgEting at Regional scale
Project partner	[Partner Acronym]
Project duration	January 2025-December 2028
Funding and grant agreement	Horizon Europe, GA, 101181873

INTRODUCTION

As part of NPower project, videos, audios and photographs may be recorded during the meetings and related activities such as workshops and events, aimed at project documentation, promotional activities and other related purposes.

The collected data will be used for research and project purposes only and always while protecting the identity of participants. Wherever possible, images or recordings will be anonymized or used in a way that does not disclose identifiable personal information unless explicit permission is provided

This documentation will be collected to document and promote the work carried out, showcasing the project's progress, share the results with the NPower community and promote sustainable management of N and P assets. The photos and videos may appear in reports, presentations, website, social media and other promotional materials, and educational resources.

The NPower project is committed to upholding the highest ethical standards in all activities, in particular: respect for autonomy, confidentiality, non-discrimination, transparency and data protection compliance.

USE OF IMAGES/RECORDINGS

I understand that the images/recordings may be used for project documentation, educational content, promotional activities, and other related purposes.

I agree that these images/recordings may be used without any further approval from me.

Duration of Consent

This consent is valid indefinitely for project-related activities unless revoked in writing.

Revocation will apply to future use of your images/recordings but cannot retroactively affect materials already published or disseminated.

No Compensation

I understand that I will not receive any monetary compensation for my participation or for the use of images/recordings.

Revocation of Consent

I understand that I may revoke this consent at any time by providing written notice to the

Rights and Ownership

I understand that the NPower project and its affiliates will own the rights to these images/recordings and may use them in any lawful and project-related manner, such as in reports, educational resources, promotional materials, or social media posts

Voluntary Participation

My agreement to participate and allow photography/recording is completely voluntary, and I am free to withdraw my consent at any time.

Release of Liability

I release the NPower project, its coordinators, and affiliates from any claims, damages, or liability arising from the use of my image/voice/likenes

I, _____, hereby declare to be of legal age (over 18 years old) and agree to be photographed and/or recorded as part of the NPower project activities

Participant's Information:

Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

I have received a copy of this agreement. This consent form is made pursuant to the relevant national, European data protection laws and regulations and personal data treatment obligations.

